

Synthesis and characterization of some Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes with 2-phenylbenzimidazole

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Abstract : Complexes of 2-phenylbenzimidazole (L) with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} of composition [ML₂X₂] (M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} and X = Cl, Br or NCS) have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared, electronic and EPR spectral data. The electronic, IR spectral data and magnetic properties suggest pseudotetrahedral structure for Co^{II} and Ni^{II}, distorted octahedral for Cu^{II} and planar geometry for Pd^{II} complexes.

Keywords : Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, 2-phenylbenzimidazole, synthesis, characterization, magnetic, IR, UV, EPR.

Introduction

The chemistry and physiological activities of benzimidazole derivatives and their metal complexes have been the subject of investigations in recent years due to their biological action against different bacteria, fungi and microbes¹. The complexes of benzimidazole, substituted benzimidazole and related ligands have been reported from this laboratory²⁻⁵ and by other workers^{6,7}. In present work, we have observed that 2-phenylbenzimidazole (PBZ) (Fig. 1) possessing a bulky phenyl group adjacent to donor benzimidazole nitrogen coordinates with Co^{II}, Ni^{II},

Fig. 1

Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} by taking only two molecules of the ligand, forming complexes of the formulae M(PBZ)₂X₂ (where M = Co^{II} when X = Cl or Br and M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Pd^{II} when X = Cl, Br or NCS). The stable complexes of Mn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{II} or Fe^{III}, VO^{II} etc. with PBZ could not be isolated in ethanol or common solvents.

Results and discussion

Cobalt(II) as well as copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes dissociate in water or aqueous ethanol liberating free PBZ. From these observations, it is inferred that bulky substituent group of ligand produces a larger steric crowding near metal ions than benzimidazole²⁻⁶ which presumably prevents the formation of stable complexes in many cases as well they interfere the accommodation of more than two coordinated ligand molecules around metal ions.

The complexes are fairly soluble in dioxane and dimethyl formamide (DMF). The electrical conductance value of complexes in DMF at 30–31 °C occurs in the range of 6–8 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm². The negligible electrical conductance value of complexes suggested coordinated nature of anions.

Palladium(II) complexes [Pd(PBZ)₂X₂] (X = Cl, Br or NCS) are diamagnetic and therefore, it is inferred that they are planar with dsp² covalent hybrid bonding. The electronic absorption spectra of [Pd(PBZ)₂X₂] (X = Cl, Br or NCS) do not show absorption band in the visible region; probably d-d transitions are enveloped in ligand absorption or charge transfer band. At room temperature, copper(II) complexes display magnetic moment values between 1.86 and 1.90 B.M., indicating that these complexes are magnetically dilute^{8,9}. The solid reflectance spectra of complexes show a strong band between

23540–23830 as well as a weak asymmetric broad band in the region 13300–11120 cm^{-1} . The former is assigned to charge transfer transition while the latter is d-d transition^{10,11} in tetragonally distorted octahedral field, assignable to ${}^1B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ transitions as broad band.

EPR spectra :

The EPR spectra at room temperature of polycrystalline CuL_2Cl_2 and CuL_2Br_2 displays g_{\parallel} at 2.261 and 2.232 while g_{\perp} tensor at 2.069 and 2.078 respectively. The g_{av} values of complexes are 2.135 and 2.218 respectively. The G parameter calculated for CuL_2Br_2 is 3.79 and that of CuL_2Cl_2 is 2.97 respectively. That G value for bromo product indicated no metal-metal interaction ($G \sim 4$) while appreciable metal-metal interaction is indicated in dichloro complexes ($G > 3$)^{12–14}. The EPR results indicated that there is a tetragonal elongation in the field and unpaired electron is located in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital and ligand nitrogen atom is bonded at axial position¹⁴.

The magnetic moment value of Ni^{II} complexes occur in the range 3.23–3.38 B.M. and reflectance spectrum showed strong band at 470–510 and 690–740 nm attributable to ${}^3T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_2 (F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_2$ transitions in approximately tetrahedral environment of ligand molecules around Ni^{II} atom^{11,15}.

Cobalt(II) complexes display magnetic moment values ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.48\text{--}4.68$ B.M.) similar to tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes^{15,16}. In methanol, the complexes $\text{Co}(\text{PBZ})_2\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or NCS) display a strong absorption band ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 230\text{--}335$) in the region 16130–15380 cm^{-1} and a shoulder near 17240–16660 cm^{-1} . The band is assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$ transition in tetrahedral field and shoulder is attributed to a split band of ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transition under the influence of spin orbit coupling in tetragonal field¹⁷. The reflectance spectra of cobalt(II) complexes are almost similar to the absorption band in methanol indicating tetrahedral structure both in solid and solution phase.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{PBZ})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{PBZ})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ display a strong and broad band at ~ 2085 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ and a medium band at ~ 790 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibrations. The $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ vibrations of $[\text{Pd}(\text{PBZ})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ is observed as strong and broad band at 2105 and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ at 795 cm^{-1} . The broadness of $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ and frequencies of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibration indicated N-bonding of thiocyanate group¹⁸. Palladium(II) is class 'b' metal

but thiocyanate is bonded to it through nitrogen instead of sulphur atom. Here, it appears that class 'b' character of Pd^{II} has been altered due to bulky volume of ligand molecule¹⁹. On the basis of the above evidences the structure of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes with the ligand 2-phenylbenimidazole have been assigned as follows (Figs. 2 and 3).

$[\text{M}(\text{PBZ})_2\text{X}_2]$ (Tetrahedral)

($\text{M} = \text{Co}^{II}$ or Ni^{II} and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or NCS)

Fig. 2

$[\text{Pd}(\text{PBZ})_2\text{X}_2]$ (Trans planar)

($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or NCS)

Fig. 3

Experimental

Preparation of ligand :

Ligand was prepared by condensing *o*-phenylenediamine with molar ratio of benzoic acid in 4 *N* HCl as reported in literature⁴. Metal salts used were AR grade reagent of BDH. Dried samples were used for all physi-

cal and spectral measurements. Elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, UV and IR spectra were recorded as reported earlier^{2,4}. The ESR spectra of complexes in powdered form at room temperature were recorded at X-band frequency on a Varian E-112 E-line century series ESR spectrophotometer.

Preparation of complexes :

[Cu(PBZ)₂X₂] (X = Cl or Br) : The complexes were obtained as yellowish green or dark brown shining crystals when copper(II) halides (1 mmol) dissolved in dry methanol (40–50 ml) were treated with 2 mmol of ligand dissolved in 30 ml hot methanol. The mixed solution stirred for fifteen minutes when crystalline dihalo complexes separated gradually. The product was filtered, washed with methanol and dried in air.

[M(PBZ)₂X₂] (M = Ni^{II} or Co^{II}; X = Cl, Br or NCS) : Appropriate metal(II) salt (1 mmol) dissolved in dry ethanol (50–60 ml) was refluxed with 1 : 2 molar proportion of ligand on a steam bath for half an hour. The resulting deep blue solution was concentrated to a small volume when blue tary mass was obtained. The product was titrated with dry ether when blue fine crystalline powder separated. It was filtered, washed with ether and dried *in vacuo*.

[Pd(PBZ)₂X₂] (X = Cl, Br or NCS) : An aqueous ethanolic solution of Pd^{II} halide (pH 3–6) was refluxed with ethanolic solution of the ligand in requisite proportion for about half an hour when light yellow product separated. The diisothiocyanato complex separated as a cream yellow product when an aqueous solution of Pd^{II} chloride containing slight excess of KCNS was refluxed with ethanolic solution of the ligand in requisite proportion. The products were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in air. The results of elemental analysis and magnetic moment values of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes

Complex (L = PBZ)/ Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	Metal	Nitrogen	Halogen	
CuL ₂ Cl ₂ Yellowish green	11.85 (12.15)	10.41 (10.71)	13.83 (13.56)	1.89
CuL ₂ Br ₂ Deep brown	10.01 (10.39)	9.49 (9.16)	26.21 (25.99)	1.86
CoL ₂ Cl ₂ Blue	11.21 (11.37)	10.44 (10.81)	13.51 (13.68)	4.58

Table-1 (contd.)

CoL ₂ Br ₂ Deep blue	9.57 (9.71)	9.34 (9.22)	26.36 (26.19)	4.68
CoL ₂ (NCS) ₂ Deep blue	10.67 (10.38)	14.66 (14.90)	-	4.48
NiL ₂ Cl ₂ Greenish yellow	10.97 (11.32)	10.53 (10.77)	13.46 (13.63)	3.28
NiL ₂ Br ₂ Greenish yellow	9.76 (9.81)	9.23 (9.35)	26.93 (26.68)	3.38
NiL ₂ (NCS) ₂ Bluish green	10.77 (10.39)	15.93 (15.40)	-	3.23
PdL ₂ Cl ₂ Light yellow	18.63 (18.81)	9.62 (9.91)	12.68 (12.53)	Dia.
PdL ₂ Br ₂ Cream	16.08 (16.25)	8.39 (8.55)	12.31 (12.20)	Dia.
PdL ₂ (NCS) ₂ Cream	17.62 (17.41)	13.91 (13.75)	-	Dia.

References

- (a) N. Fahmi and R. V. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 805; (b) M. D. Joshi, P. S. Upadhyay and A. Bani, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2000, **39**, 967; (c) N. K. Singh and S. K. Kushawaha, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1070; (d) N. K. Singh, A. Srivastava and A. M. Kayastha, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1074.
- S. P. Ghosh and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1145.
- S. P. Ghosh, P. Bhattacharjee, L. Dubey and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 230.
- S. P. Ghosh and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 212.
- (a) S. P. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 710; (b) S. P. Ghosh and A. Mishra, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 4199; (c) A. K. Sinha, Urmila Kumari, C. P. Singh and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 985; (d) C. K. Choudhary, Ratan K. Choudhary and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 761.
- (a) D. M. L. Goodgame, M. Goodgame and C. W. R. Canhan, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1972, **6**, 245; (b) Rajani Sinha and L. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 500; (c) J. S. Crossert, D. L. Hooper, K. Ramaiah and J. Ramanatham, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 140.
- (a) G. N. Mukherjee and H. K. Sahu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 209; (b) Tahira Banu, Sonal Rajora, Dilip Khatri and G. L. Talesara, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 300; (c) M. Neelamma, B. Bharat Kumar and P. Venkateshwar Rao, *Bull. Pure Appl. Sci.*, 2002, **21C**, 53; (d) P. C. Vyas, Y. K. Chahar, Yajula Garg and Gita Seth, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 843; (e) R. S. Varma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 627; (f) S. Tehlan, S. Upadhyay and Pavan Mathur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 1123; (g) Vijay Kumar,

- Neeraj Sharma, Meena, Maridula Thakur and S. C. Choudhary, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 691.
8. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry". Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1988.
 9. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Complexes", John Wiley Interscience, 1978.
 10. L. Sacconi and H. Ciampolini, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 276.
 11. E. Forster and D. M. L. Goodgame, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 823.
 12. B. J. Hathaway, I. M. Procter and P. N. Cholls, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1678.
 13. B. J. Hathaway and D. E. Billing, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 143.
 14. A. Syamal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 719.
 15. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 37.
 16. F. A. Cotton, D. M. L. Goodgame and M. Goodgame, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4690.
 17. R. Stahl-brade and W. Low, *Phys. Rev.*, 1959, **112**, 175.
 18. A. Turco and C. Pecile, *Nature*, 1961, **191**, 66.
 19. F. Basalo and J. L. Burmeister, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 1578.